

CAPTURE THE FLAG AND CYBERSECURITY EMPLOYABILITY

THE ROLE OF CTFs AS A TOOL FOR SKILL DEVELOPMENT AND INCREASED
EMPLOYABILITY FOR JUNIOR CANDIDATES IN CYBERSECURITY

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1 ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore how participation in Capture the Flag (CTF) competitions can prove beneficial for technical skill development and increase employability among cyber security students and junior candidates. Using qualitative methods, insights were gathered from two key groups – students participating in a CTF and employers and recruiters involved in cybersecurity.

The analysis of the gathered data is grounded in signaling theory, employability theory and constructivist learning theory, and examines how students perceive the learning value of CTFs, how CTF experience is interpreted during recruitment, and to what extent CTFs can compliment or serve as an alternative to formal education and work experience.

Findings show that the student group view CTFs as an effective hands-on method to apply and test theoretical knowledge as well as develop both technical and soft skills. The employer group regard CTF experience as a positive signal of motivation, problem-solving ability, and passion for cybersecurity – qualities that also match their priorities when recruiting for junior positions.

While generally not viewed as a substitute for formal education, CTF experience was recognised as a valuable complement that help strengthen the candidate's position in the recruitment process and job market – especially when traditional work experience is either lacking or minimal.

2 INTRODUCTIONS

Many junior tech talents struggle to enter the job market, despite having relevant education. An article from career marketplace platform *Dice* from November 2023 highlights how a report from *Hackajob* found that only 14% of advertised positions were junior roles. With that in mind, the intent of this study is not to examine the reasons behind this trend, but to explore how participation in activities such as Capture the Flag (CTF) competitions can improve student's and junior candidate's chances of entering the job market. The study will examine the value of CTFs from both the perspective of students and of employers involved in cybersecurity recruitment.

My hope is that this study will prove valuable both to decision-makers within the educational system and to employers in the cybersecurity field. Additionally, I believe the study can offer useful insights for students by highlighting how engagement in activities such as Capture the Flag challenges may improve their employability and attractiveness in the job market.

The study also explores how students themselves perceive their participation in CTFs as a tool to deepen their technical skills and increase their employability. To explore this, the study takes a dual-perspective approach, collecting qualitative insights from both students and employers.

The theoretical framework of this study is grounded in signaling theory, employability, and constructivist learning theory – which will be explained further in the next chapter. Together, these theories offer different but complementary ways of understanding the value of participating in CTFs – from how they support hands-on learning to how they can send important signals to employers in a competitive job market.

3 BACKGROUND AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 CAPTURE THE FLAG

Capture the Flag (CTF) is a type of competition where participants engage in a gamified version of cybersecurity problem-solving. In a safe and controlled environment, they practice ethical hacking across various areas such as forensics, web exploitation, cryptography, reverse engineering, and binary exploitation.

The competition is based on the concept of identifying and exploiting vulnerabilities to uncover hidden "flags" – often in the form of text strings – which serve as proof that the challenge has been successfully solved.

3.2 EMPLOYABILITY

In the context of this study, employability will be referred to as an individual's attractiveness on the job market. Yorke (2004) describes an individual's employability as a set of achievements, skills and understanding, as well as their personal attributes and ability to successfully present these values in a recruitment process – and thereby use them as a means to gain employment.

Furthermore, the author highlights that “employability is not merely an attribute of the new graduate. It needs to be continuously refreshed throughout a person's working life” (Yorke, 2004, p. 3) and emphasizes that the concept of employability not only concerns the individual's capacity to acquire a job, but also their ability to function and perform in a job.

3.3 SIGNALING THEORY

Signaling theory in relation to the job market was introduced by Michael Spence in 1973. The theory builds on the idea of a sending party (e.g. the jobseeker) and a receiving party (the employer), where the sender signals different attributes, competences and potentials to the receiver – through education, certificates and previous work experiences as well as other potential achievements they choose to present.

Since the receiver has limited knowledge about the sender, they will interpret these achievements and signs of experience and knowledge as signals for other capabilities in the sender. These signals could for example be indicators of the individual's trustworthiness, social skills, level of endurance, willingness to work hard or as an indication of passion and interest in the relevant subject. A diploma from a respected school could for example be a strong signal of an individual's productivity and prospects of succeeding at a workplace – even if the employer has no actual information about the candidate's specific achievements.

3.4 CONSTRUCTIVIST LEARNING THEORY

Constructivism has been discussed by a multitude of authors through the years, such as Piaget (1950), Vygotsky (1978) and Bruner (1966) and is a learning theory which proposes that knowledge is not passively received from teacher to student but actively constructed by the individual. According to this perspective, learners build understanding based on their prior knowledge, experiences, and interactions with the world around them (Kim, 2005).

The theory suggests that learning becomes most effective when individuals are actively engaged in practical hands-on tasks, problem-solving, and reflection. This makes the learning process more meaningful and personal, rather than a mechanical or repetitive memorization of facts without a deeper understanding of the subject.

4 AIM AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

4.1 AIM

The aim of this study is to examine the value of practical activities such as Capture the Flag (CTF) competitions as a tool for learning and developing technical skills within the field of cybersecurity.

Furthermore, the study aims to explore how participation in CTFs is perceived by employers during recruitment, and whether they can function as a signal of attributes valued by employers – such as interest, practical skills, or commitment – and thereby strengthen junior candidate’s employability.

By combining insights from both students and employers, this study seeks to provide a broader and more comprehensive understanding of CTFs as a potential tool both for learning and positioning in the job market.

4.2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main research question and outline of this study is:

- How can participation in CTF contests contribute to the development of technical skills and enhance student’s employability within the field of cybersecurity?

To address this foundational question, the study will investigate the following sub-questions:

1. In what ways do students perceive that their technical skills and understanding of cybersecurity are developed through CTF participation?
2. How do employers perceive CTF experience when recruiting for cybersecurity roles?
3. What personal attributes and signals do employers associate with CTF participation?
4. Can CTF participation serve as a complement or alternative to formal education or work experience for junior cybersecurity candidates?

5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND DATA COLLECTION

This study adopts a qualitative and exploratory approach, where the aim was to explore individual perceptions and experiences on the value of CTF contests, rather than to evaluate a hypothesis. An interpretive perspective was used to better understand how both participants and employers view CTF participation.

The research design is descriptive and non-experimental and focuses on capturing subjective insights from two key groups – students and cybersecurity employers and recruiters.

The data was collected using online surveys, and two separate surveys were distributed – one targeting students who were participating in a CTF competition, and one targeting industry professionals in cybersecurity. The questions were open-ended and designed to evoke personal reflection on experiences, perceptions, and attitudes towards CTF participation in both key groups. The method of data collection was used to gather as many individual perspectives as possible in a structured and analysable format.

A purposive sampling method was used to ensure relevance from both key groups, and the participation was voluntary. The survey was distributed to the student group in addition to a CTF they participated in, guaranteeing that all respondents had experience in CTF participation.

The CTF that the student group participated in was developed by me and three fellow students specifically for the purpose of this study. It was designed to be beginner-friendly and to cover a variety of common vulnerabilities, with a focus on web application exploitation. The challenges included vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, OS command injection, Insecure Direct Object References (IDOR), Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF), file upload vulnerabilities and path traversal, among others.

To reach the second group, social media platform LinkedIn was used to reach the targeted group, who then voluntarily answered the survey. Furthermore, the student survey was anonymous, while the survey targeting employers had optional anonymity. This was an intentional choice, to maintain a possibility of follow-up questions as this group had fewer participants. None such questions were needed. The final sample included thirty-five respondents in the student group and eight respondents in the employer group.

The responses were analysed using thematic analysis, and the answers were grouped by theme and aligned with the study's research questions. Recurring patterns in the answers were identified and discussed, and the responses were compared between the two groups to identify similarities and differences.

5.2 SURVEY QUESTIONS

As mentioned above, the two key groups received surveys designed to gain insights from their individual perspective in the role of either student or employer. The questions targeting the employer group included what types of experience or qualifications they value the most when

hiring for junior positions in cybersecurity, how they view CTF experience among candidates and what qualities or potential it signals. Furthermore, it included questions on how CTF participation would influence their hiring decisions and how they balance formal education and hands-on experience in the recruitment process.

The survey designed to target cybersecurity students participating in CTF contests focused on how they perceived that CTFs contributed to their technical and personal development, how it affected their understanding of theoretical knowledge gained from standard education and how CTFs as a tool for learning differ from traditional cybersecurity education methods. The survey also contained questions about whether they view CTF participation as an investment in their future career and what, if any, qualities they believe it signals to potential employers.

5.3 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Participation in the study was voluntary, and all participants were made aware of the purpose behind the survey before responding. For target group one, the students, no identifiable data was collected, and anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the research process.

The second target group, the employers, were offered optional anonymity, were most chose not to be anonymous. For the publication of this study, I have chosen to exclude any identifiable personal data from this group as well and only present their respective titles.

This study is subject to certain limitations, including the use of self-reported data resulting in some responses may reflect personal bias or limited experience with CTFs. Another factor of limitation is the limited sample size – the findings may not be generalisable beyond the context of the respondents.

6 RESULTS

6.1 STUDENTS PERCEIVED TECHNICAL SKILL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH CTF

In fact, all the students who participated in the CTF and completed the survey viewed their participation positively in terms of skill development.

The most common response was that the CTF helped them better understand, apply, and deepen their theoretical knowledge through practical experience. As one student described it:

[It helped me] hone the things I already know but rarely get to use on live engagements.

Another student emphasized how the CTF not only provided and opportunity for them to apply existing knowledge in a hands-on way but also contributed to a broader and deeper understanding of theoretical concepts, stating that it allowed them to expand their basic knowledge of certain technologies.

This was supported by several other students who described how the challenges required them to actively seek out information about vulnerabilities, tools, and techniques in order to solve the tasks.

Furthermore, many respondents felt that participating in the CTF was beneficial for their personal development as well. Areas mentioned included analytical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, and even confidence building. One student reflected:

Participating in this particular CTF has been a huge confidence boost. I came in with extremely low expectations and ended up at the top.

6.2 STUDENTS VIEWS ON CTF AS A CAREER INVESTMENT

The majority of students viewed their CTF participation as an investment in their future careers – both in terms of developing relevant skills, gaining practical experience, and standing out in the recruitment process.

Many believed that participating in CTFs demonstrates dedication, determination, and a genuine passion for the cybersecurity field. One student described their involvement as a way to build and strengthen their profile and professional reputation within the industry, while another highlighted how the experience helped them gain a better understanding of what the cybersecurity industry offers, and which areas are of most interest to them.

Several respondents noted that they believe CTF participation signals a willingness to go beyond basic academic requirements, referring to it as something they pursue outside of their formal education to further develop themselves.

Many also emphasized the importance of keeping their skills up to date and continuous learning, and viewed CTF participation as an important part of that effort:

Participating in CTFs is completely aligned with my career and I see it as a means of keeping my skills up and learning new things.

While most students viewed their participation as beneficial to their career development, a few respondents did not view it as an investment in their future career, but as one student described it – “a fun event to learn new exploits and techniques”.

6.3 EMPLOYERS PERCEPTIONS OF CTF IN THE HIRING PROCESS

When hiring for junior positions, all participating employers and recruiters agreed that CTF experience was viewed positively, and most described it as either highly beneficial or, in some cases, crucial to their hiring decision.

When asked what types of experience or qualifications they value most in junior candidates, recurring themes included hands-on experience, baseline technical knowledge, passion, and a willingness to learn. Several respondents also highlighted the importance of soft skills such as

communication and social competence. Less than 40% of respondents mentioned certifications as a decisive factor in hiring decisions.

In addition, CTF participation was considered concrete evidence of interest, practical ability, and personal initiative.

Respondents also noted that CTF experience is often useful during interviews – both as a way for employers to gain an understanding a candidate’s technical level, and as an opportunity for the candidate to demonstrate their engagement, especially when lacking formal experience.

Some scepticism was expressed, particularly regarding the depth of the candidate’s CTF experience. One respondent explained that it is common for applicants to mention a strong interest in CTFs “when in fact they have only signed up to Hack the Box or TryHackMe and tried it a little”.

6.4 CTF AS A SIGNAL OF PERSONAL ATTRIBUTES

When asked what message CTF experience sends during a recruitment process and what qualities or potential it might signal, all respondents described it as a marker of positive and desirable traits in a candidate.

The most frequently mentioned attributes signalled were passion, self-motivation, and a willingness to learn. CTF participation was also seen as a strong indicator of curiosity, problem-solving ability, and analytical thinking.

Several employers emphasized that it reflects initiative and effort beyond academic requirements and may also demonstrate collaboration and communication skills – particularly when the competitions are team-based.

One employer noted that CTF participation does not only reflect talent, passion, and hands-on ability, but also “a willingness to go beyond tutorials and tackle real-world problem-solving”.

6.5 CTF AS A COMPLEMENT OR ALTERNATIVE TO FORMAL WORK EXPERIENCE AND EDUCATION

The consensus among the employers was that CTF participation was considered a valid demonstration of skills and engagement, as well as adding value and strengthening a candidate’s profile. It was considered especially important in junior candidates where formal work experience is often lacking.

Furthermore, several respondents expressed a willingness to hire junior candidates based on alternative forms of demonstrated competence. One employer expressed that they had “hired candidates lacking formal education based on irregularly gained experience – not solely based on CTF experience, but it has been a large part of it”, and another respondent stated that they would “rather employ a passionate CTF-player than a candidate that only has formal experience from education. At least for junior roles”.

Other employers had a different view of the importance of CTF experience in the hiring process and expressed that even though CTF participation would positively influence their hiring decision, it was considered more of a complement rather than a decisive factor or enough on its own. It was also mentioned by multiple respondents that technical tests or assessments of the candidate's skills carried more weight in their final decision.

A few respondents pointed out the fact that the level of the position is closely related to the value of CTF experience – while they believed it to be highly beneficial for junior positions, its value lessened in relation to more experienced positions:

For more senior roles, it wouldn't be the same. But for someone entering the field, it can make a big difference.

7 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 PRACTICAL LEARNING THROUGH CTF IN LIGHT OF CONSTRUCTIVIST THEORY

As previously described, the theory of constructivist learning rests on the belief that knowledge is dynamic and actively constructed through experience, reflection and problem-solving. The theory assumes that it is through this active learning process that the “learner” internalises knowledge and understanding, as opposed to the view of the learner as a passive listener and receiver of knowledge.

In the light of this theory, CTF contests could be viewed as an example of a rich environment for learning through its interactive concept.

As seen in the results of the survey distributed to the students, 100% of the students perceived CTF participation as beneficial to their technical and personal development, and many motivated this by describing that the challenges forced them to independently seek out information they believed would help them solve the tasks.

Additionally, several students highlighted that the challenges not only allowed them to gain new knowledge but was also a way for them to test and deepen their theoretical understandings in a practical environment. This can be seen as an example of the students actively putting their previous knowledge in a meaningful context, and thereby better internalising that knowledge – which in turn would be an illustration of the central concept of constructivism.

Furthermore, it could be of interest to explore how student's engagement and motivation for learning might be affected by the competitive nature of CTFs. This is unfortunately not touched upon in the survey for this study but could be an area that might prove beneficial to study further – especially in terms of the value of CTFs as a complement to more formal and theoretical education.

7.2 CTF PARTICIPATION AS A SIGNAL: INTERPRETATIONS

As seen in the results, there was a consensus between the employers that CTF participation was a strong signal for passion and interest in the cybersecurity field. They went on to list traits such as curiosity, motivation, initiative, and problem-solving abilities as being signalled through the CTF engagement. Noteworthy are that these traits are among the same qualities they previously described as the most prioritised in junior candidates.

As previously mentioned, several students also reflected over what they believed their engagement in CTFs signalled to potential employers and hoped that it would be seen as an indicator of a willingness to go beyond the basic academic requirements, pointing out that CTF participation is something they do outside of their formal education. Considering signaling theory, it is interesting to note that the students are using CTFs not only as a way to gain and deepen knowledge, but also to strategically position themselves in the job market and increase their visibility.

It was also noted among the employers that the level of participation was equally as important – superficial claims of CTF experience were met with scepticism, while a deeper engagement was perceived as a strong signal for dedication and practical skills and viewed in a much more positive light.

Additionally, the findings of this study suggest that CTF participation is not only a signal and indicator of positive traits, but also a reflection of actual skill development. It is both a message and a meaningful investment in competence, displaying a parallel between both perceived and actual employability.

7.3 CTF AND EMPLOYABILITY: BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS

Employability theory (Yorke, 2004) suggests that employability is built and shaped by a combination of factors, such as knowledge, skills, and personal qualities – as well as their ability to present and use them to their advantage when applying for jobs.

As discussed previously, several students participating in this study mention CTFs as a way to strategically position themselves on the job market, indicating that they use it to strengthen their employability capital. They describe how they view CTF experience as a form of career investment, helping them build profiles that demonstrate both technical competence as well as initiative and a strong passion for the field of cybersecurity. This indicates that CTFs could help build multiple dimensions of employability, ranging from actual knowledge and competence to soft skills, attributes, and experiences, and might provide a bridge for students with little or no work experience.

As mentioned before, the employer group generally confirmed that CTFs can positively influence students or junior candidate's employability and affect their hiring decision. However, multiple employers also stressed the fact that CTF experience alone was not enough to land a position but should be viewed as a complementary experience. Some respondents highlighted that they would hire CTF players without a formal education, but those were not a

majority in this study. A combination of hands-on practices such as CTFs, formal education, technical interviews and in some cases, certifications seem to be preferred among the respondents. Interestingly, mainly employers involved in defensive security highlighted certifications as important for their hiring decision, indicating that the importance of those credentials vary depending on what kind of cybersecurity work the position involves.

One employer reflected over the importance of traditional education versus self-directed learning:

A formal degree from a reputable institution remains a strong indicator that someone can learn complex material and see long-term projects through to completion. It's a signal of persistence, structure, and the ability to navigate theoretical frameworks. However, a degree alone doesn't guarantee practical ability or curiosity beyond the classroom.

In relation to the research question concerning whether CTF participation could serve as a complement or alternative to formal education or work experience for junior cybersecurity positions, the answers among the respondents of this study strongly suggest that CTFs could prove greatly beneficial to junior candidates. While it may not always be sufficient on its own, they significantly contribute to an increased employability by displaying relevant competencies and personal drive – qualities that may not be visible through traditional qualifications alone.

In summary, CTFs could be considered one of several valid pathways into cybersecurity. They represent an accessible, practice-based alternative that supports a more inclusive and skill-oriented view of employability. One employer summarized this perspective well:

The democratization of learning through open labs and online resources has made it easier than ever to build those [technical] skills, and I believe our hiring processes should reflect that accessibility.

While not universally sufficient, it is evident that hands-on, challenge-based experience through CTFs can help bridge the gap for candidates lacking conventional backgrounds or formal experience.

7.4 PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS OF THE RESULTS

As mentioned in the beginning of this study, my hopes were to provide insights for decision-makers within the educational system as well as for students and employers involved in cybersecurity. I believe the findings of the study could serve as a basis for improving both educational strategies and recruitment practices within the field of cybersecurity.

For educators, the findings and insights presented can contribute to an increased understanding of the importance of practical and hands-on activities, as a part of preparing students for entering a competitive job market.

Additionally, an integration of practical activities such as CTFs should not only be considered beneficial to student's technical abilities, but also to strengthen their confidence, motivation, and positioning on the cybersecurity job market.

For recruiters and employers, the study suggests that CTF experience can provide a valuable complementary signal in their assessment of candidates – particularly considering junior positions where formal work experience in the candidates is often lacking or minimal.

By actively recognizing CTF experience as a legitimate and valued merit, employers will not only broaden their selection of possible candidates but also help strengthen both competence and diversity within the cybersecurity field. Acknowledging alternative pathways into the field opens the doors for candidates from different backgrounds and thereby contributing to a more inclusive, representative, and diverse cybersecurity industry.

From a student perspective, the findings of this study could offer insight and guidance on how CTF participation can be used as a tool not only for learning, but to increase their visibility and strengthen their CV with practical experience. By documenting their participation through reports and write-ups they can strategically position themselves as passionate and motivated candidates – and thereby increase their employability and career capital even when lacking formal work experience.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates how Capture the Flag (CTF) competitions may serve as a valuable and important bridge between theoretical knowledge and practical experience in the field of cybersecurity.

From a student perspective, CTFs are regarded as a highly effective learning tool, that not only introduces new knowledge, but also serve as an environment that allows them to practically apply previously known theoretical concepts and reinforce their understanding of these concepts.

Furthermore, the students in this study perceived their CTF participation as a way to signal passion, competence, and initiative to future employers – a perception that is confirmed by the participating recruiters and employers.

The employers generally regarded CTF experience as a highly positive indicator of motivation, curiosity, and practical abilities – especially regarding junior positions. While CTF participation by itself may not always be enough to secure an employment, it was seen as a significant and valuable complement to formal education, as well as a potential decisive factor for candidates lacking work experience.

The study illustrates how CTFs are not only a valuable tool for building technical skills, but also for increasing visibility and employability in the cybersecurity job market. For students and junior candidates seeking to enter this competitive job market, CTFs offer an accessible way to build both competence and confidence.

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicates that CTFs represent a valuable and promising tool for learning as well as career development – suggesting it could play a larger role in bridging the gap between education and employment in the cybersecurity industry.

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